

PERFORMANCE OF BUD-CHIP METHOD FOR YIELD AND QUALITY OF SUGARCANE UNDER DIFFERENT PLANT SPACING

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Abstract

Bud-chip is a cost-effective sowing method in sugarcane and more than 90 percent cost on seed can be saved. In this method, nursery is developed by obtaining only bud-chip from the cane and planted in polyethylene bags. After obtaining bud-chip the remaining entire cane is marketable. This experiment was conducted during autumn 2021-22 period at Sindh agriculture university Tandojam. The nursery of sugarcane variety CPF-246 was transplanted in rows 75 cm apart at 30 cm, 45 cm and 60 cm inter-row spacing in RCBD with three replicates having plot size of 3 m × 8.5 m (25.5 m²). Significant variations were observed among studied inter row plant spacing of sugarcane. Notably, the maximum cane yield of 123.55 tons per hectare, germination count 87.14 (%) and cane stand 110.29 (000 hectare) with 45 cm inter-row spacing while lowest cane yield 91.25 tones per hectare with 30cm row space. Similarly, the excellent number of sprouts 1.70 per plant, cane length 268.33 cm, plant girth 3.94 cm was found with 60cm inter-row space closely followed by 45cm row spacing. Although the crop planted at 60 cm inter-row spacing showed highest field brix 23.18 % and crop growth rate (CGR) 9.98 g m⁻²d⁻¹ as compared to 30cm and 45cm. Therefore, it is recommended for the sugarcane growers to save 90 percent of the seed cost by using the bud-chip method by following nursery transplant at 45 cm plant spacing.

INTRODUCTION

Sugarcane (*Sachharum officinarum* L.) is economically very important cash crop of Pakistan and Sindh province as well. The survival of millions of people directly or indirectly depends on this crop (Afghan et al., 2010). Sugarcane has 3.1 percent share in value addition to agriculture and 0.6 percent contribution to GDP. It provides raw material to sugar and

allied industries (Akbar et al., 2011) and reportedly more than 4 million peoples of Pakistan are engaged with this industry (GoP, 2015).

This crop provides raw material to the sugar industries but the average yield in Pakistan is lower than developed countries of the world. The cane yield

obtained in Pakistan is 57.84 t ha⁻¹ against the yield achieved in Australia (82.4 t ha⁻¹), Brazil (78.85 t ha⁻¹), Mexico (78.2 t ha⁻¹), Thailand (75.7 t ha⁻¹), USA (75.7 t ha⁻¹), Brazil (75.2 t ha⁻¹), Philippines (73.2 t ha⁻¹), China (68.08 t ha⁻¹), India (67.4 t ha⁻¹) and Argentine (64.1 t ha⁻¹). The cane yield can be increased substantially by development of new high yielding sugarcane varieties and by adoption of improved crop production practices (Tahir and Ismail, 2016). During 2021-22, 1132 thousand hectares were reported under sugarcane cultivation producing 65.5 million tons of cane showing 4.2 percent increase over preceding year (GoP, 2015).

Sugar cane yield increase about 1.71 billion tonnes in 2008 to 1.87 billion tonnes in 2020 approximately sowing 26 million ha (FAOSTAT, 2022a). Somewhat amount of yield increase sugar cane in Brazil, India, and Pakistan where as less in China (FAOSTAT, 2022b) may very low available in the world 2023/2024 very expensive regarding yield due to more price of inorganic fertilizer and may less application lose their production. As more competition in the market farmer want to more price globally in Europe and North America (FAOSTAT, 2023)

The vegetative propagation of sugarcane is done through stem cuttings using 2-budded or 3-budded seed setts for sugarcane crop establishment at commercial scale. A healthy uniform stand is of primary importance to ensure high crop yields across crop cycle. Germination capacity is the basic element to achieve good crop stand and subsequent higher crop yields; so special emphasis need to be given for achieving a good crop stand using most effective sowing method and innovative field operations for obtaining a good seedbed (Permalloo et al. 2000; Afghan et al. 2010)

Generally, the sugarcane crop is sown in furrows using seed setts or placing seed setts in the pits of different shapes and sizes. About 250 mounds of cane seed is required for planting one hectare of sugarcane and at the existing rate of seed cane; the cost only on seed is approximately 50000 rupees. This is highest amount on cost of a single unit of sugarcane production. The cost on seed can be reduced through adoption of different methods of seed preparation. Apart from the universal method of tissue culture, bud-chip method has also been found cost effective and more than 90

percent cost on seed can be saved. In this method, the nursery is prepared by obtaining only bud-chip from the cane and planted in the polyethylene bags. After obtaining the bud-chip the remaining entire cane is marketable (Legendre, 2003).

Improper spacing between rows or plants and seeding density are the most critical factors that influence sugarcane yield (Bashir et al., 2000). The sub-optimal seeding density and improper spacing result in low plant population density that results in lower millable canes per unit area which is the key component of cane yields (Bashir et al., 2000). The high-density planting of sugarcane can improve cane and sugar yield through promoting rapid canopy closure and increasing radiation interception earlier in crop growth. Although, closer spacing results in high plant population but obstructs cultural operations (Pawar et al., 2005). So, the outcomes of sugarcane crop grown at varied spacing need to be investigated. There is a contradiction regarding the effect of row or plant spacing and seeding densities on the quality parameters such as Brix, sucrose contents, juice extraction and commercial cane sugar etc. of sugarcane (Pawar et al., 2005). Nevertheless, most of the studies depict that sugarcane quality was not affected by spacing and seeding densities (Asokan et al., 2005)

In view of the significance of cost-effective planting methods, the experiment was conducted to evaluate growth, yield and quality of sugarcane planted at different spacing and nursery developed through bud chip method, under agro-ecological conditions of Tandojam Sindh province of Pakistan

Materials and Methods

In order to evaluate growth, yield and quality of sugarcane planted at different spacing and nursery developed through bud chip method, an experiment was conducted at the students' experimental farm department of agronomy, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam during autumn 2021-2022 in RCBD with three replicates having plot size of 3 m × 8.5 m (25.5 m²). For raising seed nursery, chip-buds were prepared from sugarcane by chipper machine and the chip-buds were soaked in carbendazim @ 0.1% for 10 minutes. The treatment of bud chip is essential because with disinfection the bud may not sprout (Legendre, 2003; Chattha et al 2010). After

S/N o.	Plant Spacing	Germination (%)	Sprouts plant ⁻¹	Cane Length (cm)	Cane stand (000 ha ⁻¹)	Plant girth (cm)	Cane Yield (tons ha ⁻¹)	Field Brix (%)
1	30cm	81.27a	1.13b	255.67c	77.61b	3.76b	91.25c	20.67b
2	45cm	82.47a	1.51ab	260.31b	110.29a	3.85ab	123.55a	21.33ab
3	60cm	81.40b	1.70a	268.33a	105.13a	3.94a	107.13b	23.18a
LSD (0.05)		1.23	0.48	4.30	25.70	0.16	8.68	2.18

soaking process, the individual chip-bud was sown in polyethylene bags filled with soil media (Soil + Organic matter) at 2:1 ratio. The bud was kept in polyethylene bags under half inch soil layer and irrigated at 3-4 days interval regularly by flooding method while the sprinkled twice a day keeping the bags moist and buds fresh. The germination was started after 7 days and completed after 40 days, the seedlings were transplanted in the statistically designed experimental plots. The gaps were filled through germinated plants in polythene bags to maintain plant population. A good seedbed was prepared by adopting recommended land preparation practices. Ridges were prepared to place transplant seedlings. The fertilizer dose of fertilizer of N:P: K (118:112:112) were applied to the experiment. Completed dose of P and K was applied at the time of sowing whereas N applied in three splits. The irrigation and plant protection measure were adopted according to the requirement of crop.

Results and Discussion

In sugarcane sowing, expenditure incurred on seed by the farmer is single highest cost unit in the entire production process. The adoption of Bud chip method is although little labour intensive, but almost 90 percent cost on seed can be saved by development of nursery through bud-chip method and transplanting after seedling development. Sugarcane farmers of Pakistan are normally using traditional planting methods whereas, research findings indicted that the higher cane yields can be achieved through innovative sugarcane management practices (Viator et al. 2005). This experiment was conducted to evaluate growth, yield and quality of sugarcane planted at different inter-row spacing (30 cm, 45 cm and 60 cm) maintaining intra row spacing at 75 cm. The findings of the study are discussed hereunder:

Table 1. Germination (%), sprouts per plant, cane length, cane stand, plant girth, cane yield and field brix of sugarcane at 30,45 and 60cm inter-row spacing. The results of experiment shown in table-1 revealed that sprouting of buds initiated after 7 days of sowing in all three treatments and the germination (%) was recorded from 81.27% to 82.47% at different plant spacing. The differences were insignificant for these parameters. These results are in agreement with those of Ridge and Hurney (1994) who reported that spacing did not affect the days to sprouting in sugarcane; while Getaneh et al. (2016) found that sugarcane varieties differed significantly for germination but spacing did not show significant impact on germination.

Similarly, maximum tillers (1.70 stool⁻¹) were in crop transplanted at the plant spacing of 60 cm; followed by 1.151 stool⁻¹ when transplanted at plant spacing of 45 while 1.13 tillers stool⁻¹ in case of 30 cm. Increase in the plant spacing increased the number of tillers stool⁻¹ significantly with the reason that distant seedlings availed more space that resulted in increased exposure to air and light interception coupled with increased share of soil nutrients and moisture for the individual plants. Jain et al. (2010) and Jain et al. (2011) experienced that increase in spacing resulted in increased tillers per stool. Sattar et al. (2010) showed that tillering capacity in sugarcane increased with increasing the inter and intra row spacing. Devi et al. (2011) observed that narrow planting caused decreased tillering in sugarcane varieties.

Maximum cane length was (268.33 cm) at the plant spacing of 60 cm; followed by 260.31 cm and 255.67 cm at 45 cm and 30 cm plant spacing. The increasing plant spacing caused increase in the cane length. This increase in cane length under wider spacing was mainly associated with availability of more space for individual plants and greater share of nutrients and moisture stimulated cane growth.

Similarly, cane girth was also greater (3.94 cm) when sugarcane nursery (bud-chip method) was transplanted at the plant spacing of 60 cm; followed by 3.85 cm and 3.76 cm in crop where the sugarcane seedlings were transplanted at the plant spacing of 45 cm 30 cm, respectively. The increasing plant spacing resulted in a substantial increase in cane girth. This increase in cane girth where the plant to plant spacing was greater was linked with less plant population receiving relatively higher amounts of nutrients and moisture as compared dense planting. These results are in line with those of [Zhao and Li \(2015\)](#) who reported that increased spacing resulted in improvement in cane length and cane thickness. [Selvean et al. \(2000\)](#) reported that availability of more space between rows and plants caused positive impact on cane elongation. [Molina et al. \(2005\)](#) and [Legendre \(2003\)](#) found thicker canes in plots where wider spacing was maintained for sugarcane planting. The higher cane yield of 123.55 t ha⁻¹ was found at 45 cm of plant spacing followed by 107.13 t ha⁻¹ at 60 cm plant spacing and lowest cane yield 91.25 t ha⁻¹ was recorded at the lowest plant spacing of 30 cm as shown in table-1. In case of 45 cm plant spacing; due to optimum plant population the cane yield was observed maximum from 60 cm plant spacing and 30cm. However, under 30 cm spacing, extensively dense population did not produce quality cane and hence, lower cane yield was obtained.

These results are in line with those of [Mohanty and Nayak \(2011\)](#), [Arain et al. \(2011\)](#), [Ehsanullah et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Ayele et al. \(2013\)](#) who have reported that the spacing between plants should be maintained in such a way that the desired plant population is not affected. [Baloch \(2013\)](#), [Briceno et al. \(2013\)](#) and [Ayele and Tegene \(2014\)](#) found that under wider row spacing the cane yield was decreased as compared to dense planting. This was mainly because lower plant population under wider spacing caused decline in yield.

The maximum brix content in juice (23.13%) was determined in canes where sugarcane nursery developed by bud-chip method was transplanted at 60 cm plant spacing; while brix considerably decreased (21.33%) at the inter-row spacing of 45 cm; as shown in figure 1 while minimum (20.67%) at narrow plant spacing of 30 cm. With increasing plant spacing, the brix content was increased; because under wider plant spacing the cane quality was improved mainly associated with greater space availability where plants received more nutrients and moisture as compared to narrow spacing of 30 cm where plant population excessively increased. The results of the present research regarding brix content in cane juice were in accordance to those of [Viator et al. \(2005\)](#), [Amolo and Abayo \(2007\)](#), [Muraro \(2009\)](#), [Garside and Bell \(2009\)](#) reported that increase spacing improved the cane quality and increased brix content.

Figure-1: Crop growth rate (CGR) gm⁻²d⁻¹ of sugarcane at 30,45 and 60 cm inter-row space.

The highest crop growth rate ($9.98 \text{ g m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) was determined when nursery raised through bud-chips was transplanted at the inter-row spacing of 60 cm; followed by $9.85 \text{ g m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$ and $9.65 \text{ g m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$ at the inter-row spacing of 45 cm and 30 cm as shown in fig 1. With increase in the plant spacing, the crop growth was increased significantly due to availability of more space for individual plants, because with increasing plant spacing the aeration increased with interception of light is improved. Croft (1998) reported that the crop growth rate was significantly affected by spacing and wider spacing caused more crop growth rate as compared to dense planting of sugarcane. Similarly, Saini et al. (2012) indicated that under dense planting the crop growth rate was declined.

Conclusions

It was concluded that bud-chip method showed most promising results when sugarcane nursery developed through this method and seedlings transplanted at 45 cm plant to plant spacing produced higher cane yield of 123.55 t ha^{-1} as compared to 107.13 t ha^{-1} and $91.4=25 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$ when transplanted at 60 cm and 30 cm plant spacing, respectively.

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